

Research Article

Strategic Action Plan in Higher Learning Institution – Effective Project Management

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Abstract: *Project management is a systematic technique for planning, executing, and controlling a wide range of initiatives. Strategic planning with clear objectives, roles, and milestones is vital to ensure the achievement of the strategy where it must have a clear aim, vision, and mission. UiTM2025 Strategic Plan is an extension of the UiTM 11th Malaysia Plan (2016-2020) that takes into account the most recent developments in Malaysia, particularly the higher education industry, and is centered on three Strategic Thrusts: Quality Education, Global Excellence, and Value-Driven Performance. Effective project management within a strategic action plan is essential for ensuring that the institution can adapt to changing educational landscapes, meet its goals, and provide a high-quality educational experience for its students and other stakeholders.*

Keywords: Project management; Strategic Action Plan; University Transformation Division.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) has established a comprehensive strategic plan, known as UiTM2025 (University Transformation Division, 2021), with the aim of attaining Globally Renowned University by the year 2025 (GRU2025). The strategic plan implementation involves the establishment of annual themes from 2021 until 2025, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Annual theme of UiTM2025 Strategic Plan

In order to fulfil the objectives and aspirations of UiTM, an operational strategy known as the strategic action plan (SAP) was implemented. This plan encompasses three key strategic priorities: Quality Education, Global Excellence, and Value-Driven Performance. Effective project management framework is necessary to facilitate the efficient monitoring of planned activities by top management and essential stakeholders, such as lead directors, faculties, campuses and centres of excellence. A strategic action plan is a comprehensive and structured document that delineates precise measures, initiatives, and undertakings that an organisation, team, or individual must undertake in order to attain their strategic goals and objectives (Zulch, 2014). The document functions as a navigational tool that facilitates the execution of a strategic plan, transforming overarching strategic goals into practical and achievable assignments. Effective project management within a strategic action plan is essential for ensuring that the institution can adapt to changing educational landscapes, meet its goals, and provide a high-quality educational experience for its students and other stakeholders (Gupta, Park, & Phaal, 2022).

To ensure the resounding success of GRU2025, various SAP projects have been developed and executed. In coordinating SAP projects for the year of 2024, a visionary plan has been set in motion. This plan, bearing the distinguished theme of "Globally Respected University," is anticipated to materialise through a collaboration with the UiTM Council of Professors. The brainstorming sessions of the projects were planned, employing the World Café style forum. The World Café style forum provides a straightforward, efficient, and adaptable framework for facilitating expansive collective discussions. The discussions were conducted in accordance with the six pillars of the Globally Respected University 2024, as illustrated in Figure 2.

6 PILLARS OF GLOBALLY RESPECTED UNIVERSITY 2024	1	World Class Faculty Members
	2	Turning Globally Respected Student
	3	Turning Globally Respected Staff
	4	Excellent Supporting Staff
	5	Highly Involved Industry & Community
	6	Engaging Alumni

Figure 2. Six Pillars of Globally Respected University 2024

In managing the SAP projects, a comprehensive system has been devised to facilitate the documentation and analysis of pertinent information. In the year 2020, the UiTM Project Management Office System (UePMO) was implemented, however, the operational procedures were primarily reliant on manual processes. The system underwent subsequent enhancements in 2021 and 2022, wherein new

functionalities were introduced. In the year 2023, a new system known as the UiTM Strategic Management System (UiSMS) was implemented, facilitating the organisation and systematic analysis of project information. The implementation of the module within the UiSMS system was successfully completed during the initial phase on the February 21st, 2023. The developed module pertained to the registration of projects, profiles, and budgets for all lead directors, faculties, campuses, and centres of excellence. The data collection was presented during the first quarter presentation, which took place from April 24th to 26th, 2023. The implementation of the second phase was successfully completed on July 4th, 2023. The supplementary components include activity, risk, dependency, and milestone aspects for each project that was originally recorded during phase 1. The data information was formally disclosed during the second quarter presentation held on July 26th, 2023. The developmental trajectory of SAP management systems is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Evolution of SAP management system

2. METHOD

In the context of managing SAP in higher learning institutions, (Haiyee, 2022) outlines a comprehensive framework consisting of five essential steps. These steps are *Initiating, Planning, Executing, Monitoring and Control, and Closing*.

2.1 Initiating

The generation of ideas is a critical factor in promoting innovation and facilitating progress across diverse fields. Numerous methodologies and approaches can be utilised by organisations to effectively foster the generation and acquisition of ideas. The successful implementation of the UiTM2025 Strategic Plan relies on the unwavering dedication, active involvement, and collaborative efforts of all parties involved, in order to achieve the desired goals and objectives of UiTM. Hence, it is customary for individuals occupying leadership roles, such as lead directors, deans, and rectors, to develop an annual Strategic Action Plan (SAP) with the aim of attaining their designated Performance Indicators (PI). The individuals responsible for overseeing the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) and Performance Indicator (PI) initiatives have been appropriately appointed as project directors. The main responsibility of the individual under consideration is to ensure the effective and successful implementation of the nine strategic themes. At the commencement of each year, it is of utmost importance for all relevant parties involved to actively engage in the process of developing and officially documenting their Strategic Action Plan (SAP) within the UiSMS system.

2.2 Planning

In this study, the implementation of the World Cafe style forum was employed as a method for conducting the planning steps. The World Cafe style is a highly interactive approach that has been widely utilised to effectively foster the generation and development of ideas (Löhr, Weinhardt, & Sieber, 2020; Schiele, Krummacker, Hoffmann, & Kowalski, 2022). The present study elucidates the utilisation of a structured conversational approach, which facilitates the cultivation of an environment conducive to open and intimate discourse. Additionally, this approach fosters the establishment of meaningful connections among ideas within the context of a larger collective. The objective of this procedure is to access the collective knowledge and insights that are currently available within the confines of the room. The World Cafe style is a well-established and widely recognised approach that offers a streamlined, effective, and flexible framework for facilitating in-depth group conversations. The process of generating ideas in the development of a strategic action plan involves several key steps. These steps are essential for ensuring a comprehensive and effective plan that aligns with UiTM goals and objectives. The following were the steps taken in this study:

1. The designation of group leaders to facilitate discussion within various groups. The selection process for the leaders involved members of the UiTM Council of Professors who possess expertise in various fields. These individuals were chosen to enable discussions pertaining to the design of SAP projects in alignment with the six pillars outlined in the Globally Respected University 2024 initiative.
2. The preceding leaders engaged in the proactive development of a strategic action plan in advance. The proposed plan involves engaging in a collaborative ideation process to identify and analyse various challenges pertaining to the different domains within UiTM. Additionally, the plan aims to develop effective strategies and solutions to address the identified issues.
3. On the scheduled date of the discussion, the World Café style forum was conducted in multiple rooms as per the schedule shown in Figure 4. The forum was categorised into two distinct groups. The leaders along with their respective teams remained in their rooms and engaged in a discussion pertaining to their respective domains of expertise. The alternate cohort, assuming the role of visiting participants, engaged in a rotational pattern, thereby ensuring their input was shared across all pillars of Globally Respected University 2024. Upon the completion of the forum, the resultant output generated by each group encompassed an extensive number of ideas contributed by both the attending members and their esteemed experts.

LOCATION	DURATION OF DISCUSSION					
	30 minutes	30 minutes	30 minutes	30 minutes	30 minutes	30 minutes
Room 1	Group 1	Group 6	Group 5	Group 4	Group 3	Group 2
Room 2	Group 2	Group 1	Group 6	Group 5	Group 4	Group 3
Room 3	Group 3	Group 2	Group 1	Group 6	Group 5	Group 4
Room 4	Group 4	Group 3	Group 2	Group 1	Group 6	Group 5
Room 5	Group 5	Group 4	Group 3	Group 2	Group 1	Group 6
Room 6	Group 6	Group 5	Group 4	Group 3	Group 2	Group 1

Figure 4. World Café style forum group discussion schedule

4. The projects have undergone the necessary steps to reach their final stage, where they have been consolidated into a comprehensive strategic action plan. The plan has been carefully

designed to align with and address all aspects of the UiTM2025 Strategic Plan, specifically the Globally Respected University 2024.

2.3 Executing

Execution is a stage where a project is implemented, incorporating the application of a chosen approach, method, or framework to bring to fulfilment of the project. Hence, execution refers to the implementation phase that must ensue any preceding deliberation for an event to transpire. The UiSMS system is utilised by the University Transformation Division to assess the percentage of project completion for monitoring purposes. The successful set up of SAP requires the completion of various tasks involving multiple departments. Execution of the SAP projects will begin in the early 2024.

2.4 Monitoring and Control

The UiSMS system offers a robust platform for the analysis, modification, and tracking of strategic projects. The monitoring process is an integral component of the formal procedures within the project development methodology. It has been recognised as a crucial practise that significantly contributes to the success of an open innovation project. The effective management of a project requires the ability to adapt and modify its objectives as new information becomes available. This is particularly important as the process of seeking answers may uncover data that contradicts the initial research questions. The approval of SAP is contingent upon the endorsement of the department head, thereby ensuring adherence to established protocols and guidelines. Additionally, the University Transformation Division will monitor the implementation and progress of SAP, ensuring its effective integration within the UiTM ecosystem. The progress of the project was diligently monitored and evaluated through the implementation of best practises sharing methodologies. On an annual basis, the lead directors, faculties, campuses and centres of excellence provide the necessary SAP data for the purpose of conducting quarterly analysis.

2.5 Closing

It is crucial that all lead directors, faculties, campuses and centres of excellence to be actively engaged in the regular updating of the SAP progress. Furthermore, the final report will be uploaded into the UiSMS system. The University Transformation Division is responsible for the compilation of an annual report for the university, which is scheduled to be completed at the end of the year.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the outcomes of the World Café style forum, it has been determined that a comprehensive set of 19 projects has been formulated. These projects have been carefully assigned to their respective lead directors with assistance of project directors and managers, will be responsible for overseeing their successful execution throughout the year 2024. The scope of this study comprises a comprehensive 50 sub-activities, which are categorised into quick win and long-term projects. The proposed projects based on the six pillars of Globally Respected University 2024 are as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Details of SAP projects developed from World Café Style forum

Pillars of Globally Respected University 2024	Project Name	Lead Directors
1 – World Class Faculty Members	Global Prominent Professors Legacy Programme	Office of Vice Chancellor (Research & Innovation)
	Top Researchers International Consortium (TRIC) Programme	Office of Vice Chancellor (Academic & International)
2 – Turning Globally Respected Student	UiTM i-STAR Students	Office of Vice Chancellor (Student Affairs)
3 – Turning Globally Respected Staff	Admin Going Global	Registrar
	UiTM Skill Forge	
	Standing in the eyes of the world	
4 – Excellent Supporting Staff	Talent Quest	Office of Assistant Vice Chancellor (Institute of Leadership and Development)
	UiTM Credo	
	CHAMPS@UiTM	Registrar
	Embracing Global 4 Support Staff	
5 – Highly Involved Industry & Community	UiTM ESG Gateway	Office of Vice Chancellor (Industry, Community & Alumni Network)
	UiTM iconic community project	
	UiTM International Voluntarism	
	UiTM ESG (Connectivity)	
6 – Engaging Alumni	MyAlumni Profile	Office of Vice Chancellor (Industry, Community & Alumni Network)
	My Alumni: UiTM Di Hatiku	
	MyAlumni: Come Back Home	
	MyAlumni: Second Home	Office of Vice Chancellor (Development)
	MyAlumni System	Office of Vice Chancellor (Industry, Community & Alumni Network)

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Strategic Action Plan (SAP) serves as a crucial instrument in the pursuit of objectives within higher learning institutions. The utilisation of the World Café style forum has demonstrated promising potential as a methodology for facilitating the advancement of SAP projects. The reporting of the monitoring and closure activities of the project will occur subsequent to the execution and successful completion of the project.

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